

The Rock Art of Transbaikalia: New Sites from the Uda River Basin

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The Uda River has its source on the Vitim Plateau in Transbaikalia and, after 467 km, it flows into the Selenga. To the north and west, the catchment basin of the Uda is bordered by the Ulan-Burgasy Ridge; to the east by the Vitim plateau and, to the south, by the Tsagan-Khurtey and Tsagan-Daban Ranges.

Map of the Uda River Basin (the lower reaches and tributaries of the river not covered). Blue dots indicate famous and well-documented rock art sites. Unknown rock art sites (N1 - N18) are marked in red. The orange dots mark known rock art sites (N 19/N20) which are also included in this survey.

The history of rock art research in the region covers 21 locations which were documented in a handful of surveys from the late 19th and early 20th centuries (Davydov, 1856; Kastren, 1860; Popov, 1928;) and augmented by a number of recent publications (Okladnikov and Zaporozhskaya, 1969, 1970; Tivanenko, 1979, 1990; Khamzina, 1982; Lbova and Khamzina, 1999; Tsybiktarov, 2011; Tashak, 2011, 2013; Antonova and Tashak, 2013). Between June and August 2019, we have discovered and documented 18 additional rock art sites (N1 – N18). We have also examined and described two previously known sites (N19/20).

In this report, a brief description of the abovementioned sites is provided (pp. 12 – 20), followed by the tracings of the rock art discussed (N1 – N13, pp. 22-28; N16 – N18, pp. 29-32; N19 and N20, pp. 32-33). In addition, a few photographs and enhanced D-Stretch images are also attached (N2-2, N2-3, N13-5 and N5-5; pp. 34-37).

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N1 (p. 22)

The site is located 300 m to the north of the bridge across the Kurba River, on the western outskirts of Tegda village, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia. The drawings are situated on the south-eastern face of a small cliff, on a single rocky surface (N1-1). They are painted with red mineral pigment (ocher). At a height of 1.1 m, an anthropomorphic figure (N1-1) is depicted and, above it, at a height of 1.8 m, a figure in the shape of an inverted letter Y (N1-2).

N2 (p. 22)

The rock art site is located at a distance of 4 km - in a straight line - southwest of the village of Udinsk, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia. We have counted at least 4 rock faces with ochre-painted images:

- N2-1 is situated on the south-eastern side of the rock face, centrally located and at the sole of the rock under it. Dimensions: 0.5 x 0.6 x 0.45 x 0.2 x 0.5 x 0.6 m. In the center of the composition there are two bird-like (ornithomorphic) figures, one above the other (the lower right part of the rock face). Above them, 4 cross-shaped figures, and figures of strange shapes, including two possibly anthropomorphic figures. All images are drawn with dark crimson ocher.
- N2-2 is located 0.4 m to the left of N2-1. Oriented to the southwest, its size is 0.7 x 0.3 x 0.6 x 0.25 m. The depictions, from left to right, are of an ornithomorphic figure, an anthropomorphic figure, a tiger-like zoomorphic figure, and 'fences' with dots inside.
- N2-3 is located at a distance of 0.6 m to the left and above N2-2 and it is oriented to the southwest. Dimensions: 1.15 x 0.7 x 1.2 x 0.55 m. A circle with four lines extending from it is depicted.
- N2-4 is at another 0.6 m to the left and above N2-3 and is similarly oriented to the southwest. Dimensions: 1.3 x 0.4 x 1 x 0.3 m. A circle surrounded by more than 30 dots is depicted. Inside the circle there is another dot.

N3 (p. 23)

The site is at 5.5 km – as the crow flies – to the north-northeast, in the northern outskirts of the village Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia. It is at a distance of 150 m to the north of a farm, on a mountain that locals associate with shamanistic traditions. We have discovered 3 rock faces with red ochre images:

- N3-1 is located in the middle of the cliff, if you look at it from the southeast, which is its orientation. Dimensions: 1.5 x 1.3 x 1.4 x 1.2. The figures are situated in the lower-right part of the rock face, at a height of 0.15 - 0.5 m. Two rectangular 'fences' with dots inside are shown next. In the first, six rows of 9 - 10 (?) dots, while in the second 'fence' - which is to the right of the first - 3 rows of 4 - 5 (?) dots. Above the first 'fence', under the white sag, 2 presumably ornithomorphic (bird-like)/anthropomorphic figures can be depicted.
- N3-2 is 2 m to the right of N3-1 and is similarly oriented to the southeast. Dimensions: 0.6 x 0.7 x 0.5 x 0.4 x 0.7 m. The figures are traced in the upper-right part of the rock face,

at a height of 0.7 - 0.9 m. Two anthropomorphic figures and a zoomorphic image above them are depicted.

- N3-3. Located 0.7 m to the right of N3-2 and it is oriented toward the south. Dimensions: 0.6 x 0.9 x 0.5 x 1.0 x 0.3 m. The figures are in the upper and middle parts of the face, at a height of 0.4 - 0.9 m. Two ornithomorphic figures are depicted, one above the other.

Near the cliff there are tiled graves, one at 5 m to the south, and two more at 15 m to the south-east. It is interesting to note that the latter denote the number of the 'fences' on N3-1. A further 105 steps southeast of the cliff there is a masonry built in the form of the number "8".

N4 (p. 24)

The rock art site is located 6 km north of the village Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the right bank of the Khan-Zhargalan River. At least 3 rock faces with ochre-made images were counted:

- N4-1. Oriented to the east. Dimensions: 1.2 x 1.25 x 1.6 m.
- N4-2. Situated at 19 m to the right of N4-1 and oriented to the southeast. Dimensions: 0.9 x 1.1 x 1 x 1.4 x 0.9 m. A figure resembling the shape of a tree is depicted. Above it is a figure that approximates the shape of an inverted letter «Y», and poorly preserved horizontal lines.
- N4-3 is to the right of N4-2 and it is oriented to the southeast. Dimensions: 1.4 x 0.3 x 1.1 x 0.25 x 0.7 m.

On the hillside, under the rock, there are artificial masonry remains (of the «Slab Grave Culture»), and a chipped stone made of black siliceous tuff and transparent chalcedony was also found.

N5 (p. 25)

The site is located 8.9 km - in a straight line - to the north of the village Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the right bank of the Khan-Zhargalan River, in the northern part of the rock massif, above the reservoir (see map, p. 11). Here, at least 6 rock faces with red ochre images were counted:

- N5-1. At a height of 1.2 - 1.3 m above the ground and with a south-southeast orientation. Dimensions: 1.3 x 1.5 m. A cruciform figure is depicted in the lower right. Dots can be depicted at the top of the image.
- N5-2. 1 m to the right, at a height of 0.5 m. Oriented south-southeast, its dimensions are 1.5 x 0.7 m. At the bottom there is an ornithomorphic figure with dots. In the upper part, there is probably a point or dot.
- N5-3. At 0.3 m to the right of N5-2, at a height of 1.25 m and oriented south-southeast. Dimensions: 1.0 x 0.9 m. In the center of the composition there is a cow moose and a small moose, with its head turned to the left. Between them is an ornithomorphic- and an anthropomorphic figure. Apparently, an additional zoomorphic figure is also depicted.

ed. The composition is surrounded by dots. Above and to the left, a cruciform figure is drawn. On the surface there are white smudges that overlap the image.

- N5-4 is 0.3 m below and to the right of N5-3, at a height of 0.8 m from the rocky base under it. Oriented south-southeast, its size is 0.9 x 0.55 m. In the upper part, an ornithomorphic figure is clearly visible, and under it a chaotic cluster of dots.
- N5-5. Adjacent to N5-4, to its right, at a height of 1.3 - 2.2 m from the rocky base under it. Oriented south-southeast, with a size of 2 x 1.4 m. In the lower part, two zoomorphic figures are clearly visible (on the right a moose cow, and to its left a fox-like animal). Above, in the right middle part, there are cross-shaped figures and dots. In the upper left part there are some poorly visible images, likely of dots and of a cross-shaped figure.
- N5-6, 0.5 m below N5-4, is also oriented south-southeast. Size: 0.3 x 0.3 m. In the upper part, dots are depicted.

N6 (p. 26)

The sixth site that we have surveyed is located 5.9 km to the north-east of the village Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Khan-Zhargalan River and on the southern slope of Shulut Hill. Here, we have located at least 4 rock faces with red ochre images on them:

- N6-1 is located in the middle of the cliff, if you look at it from the south-west, at height of about 2 m from the base. Oriented west-west-south, its size is 0.35 x 0.3 x 0.3 x 0.35 m. Dots are likely depicted.
- N6-2 is 0.6 m below N6-1 and is similarly oriented. Dimensions: 0.4 x 1.15 x 0.05 x 1.15 x 0.45 m. 2 pairs of anthropomorphic figures are depicted, one in the upper left part, the other in the middle of the face.
- N6-3 is located 1.5 m to the right of N6-2 and at a lower height, at the foot of the cliff on the south side. Oriented south-southeast, its dimensions are 0.15 x 0.35 x 0.45 x 0.45 x 0.25 m. In the upper part of the face a series of dots are depicted, and below them, an apparently ornithomorphic figure.
- N6-4 is 1.9 m to the right of N6-3, 1.35 - 1.7 m above the base. It is oriented straight to the south. Dimensions: 1.5 x 0.4 x 0.85 x 0.7 x 0.4 m. In the middle of the composition there are rows of dots and 3 - 4 likely ornithomorphic/anthropomorphic figures. The drawings are poorly visible.

In the vicinity of the cliff there are masonry remains («slab graves»), 2 of them to the south-west, with an additional one to the south-east.

N7 (p. 26)

This rock art site is located 9.9 km north of the village of Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Khan-Zhargalan, on Mount Huhe Baysa (from Buryat «Blue Mountain»). Here, so far, we have identified only one surface, with a red ochre image on it.

- N7-1 is located in a niche and oriented to the southwest. Its size is 2.2 x 1.4 x 1.4 x 1.2 m. In the middle part of the surface, 14 vertical lines at different angles are depicted. Two of them are partly covered by white smudges.

N8 (p. 26)

The rock art site is 9.9 km to the north of the Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of Khan-Zhargalan, on Mount Huhe Baysa and 500 m north of N7. At least one place bearing rock art was identified. This is located in the lower right part of the cliff (N8-1). The surface has a north west orientation. Dimensions: 1.65 x 1.2 x 1.4 x 0.9 m. The markings are made in red ochre. In the upper left part, a horned anthropomorphic figure with raised arms is depicted, with a sign in the form of the Cyrillic letter «Г» traced on its abdomen. A fragment of a zoomorphic or anthropomorphic figure is preserved in the upper right part of the panel.

N9 (p. 26)

This site is located 6.8 km - in a straight line - southeast of the southern outskirts of the village of Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, in the Sanny Mys (Tapkhar) area, which is 1.2 km to the west of the famous rock paintings Sanny Mys (Tivanenko, 1990, pp. 21-22). The images are located in the middle of the rock face (N9-1). Oriented to the southwest, the dimensions are 0.6 x 0.25 x 0.5 x 0.25 m. At the height of 1.1-1.2 m from the base of the rock under the surface, in our opinion, an anthropomorphic figure seems to be depicted. It is executed in red ochre and the outlines are very blurry.

N10 (p. 26)

The rock art site is located 10 km north-east of the village of Bayan-Gol, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the right bank of the Shubuguy River, and 600 m north of the famous Shubuguy site (Okladnikov and Zaporizhzhya, 1970, p. 31) and 1.4 km south of the Shubuguy site, Point 2 (Tivanenko, 1990, p. 21).

The image-bearing surface is located in the lower-right part of the rock, when seen from the south, at a height of 1 - 1.1 m from the bottom of the rock (N10-1). Oriented to the south, its size is 0.5 x 0.5 x 0.4 x 0.3 x 0.5 x 0.4 m. An anthropomorphic figure is depicted, in red ochre. There are three horns on the head of the figure and its arms are raised. The legs are spread. In our opinion, the figure portrays a female.

N11 (p. 27)

The site is located 3,9 km - in a straight line - southeast of the eastern outskirts of the village of Kulsk, in the Khorinsky district of the Republic of Buryatia, and 700 m west of the lower bridge across the Kodun (Khudan) River. The locals call this place «Torm». At least two granitic rock surfaces bear red ocher representations.

- N11-1 is located at the bottom of the cliff, more precisely, on its south-eastern side. Dimensions: 0.75 x 0.55 m. Hovering ornithomorphic figures seem to be portrayed - 16 cm from the sole of the rock, and to the right of it. In our opinion, 2 rows of 7 (but possibly 8) oval spots (dots) are outlined below the curve line. To the right, and below the dots, a vertical line is likely drawn.
- N11-2 is located 2 m to the right of N11-1, at a height of 0.45 - 0.6 m from the bottom of the cliff. Oriented east-east-north, the size is 0.4 x 0.6 m. In the upper part, there is the likelihood of an anthropomorphic figure being depicted.

Note that, unfortunately, 40 m to the north of the images there is arable land, and to the south a sand quarry.

N12 (p. 27)

The site is at 2.2 km to the north of the village of Kodunsky Stanok, in the Kizhinginsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Khudan (Kodun) River, in the Khabsagai area (which, in the Buryat language means "rock", "cliff"). In 2011, 13 slab graves, a figured grave, a «kereksur» (round mound) and a burial site were discovered here, however, rock paintings were not mentioned (*Pamyatniki arkheologii*, 2011, p. 208). Images are available on at least two granite rocks, 250 m apart from each other.

- N12-1 is located 100 m from the road, on the southernmost cliff of the area, and it is oriented exactly to the south. Dimensions: 1,25 x 0,35 x 0,25 x 0,25 x 0,75 x 0,8 m. At least 30 (point-like) dots are visible on the lower part of the block. The right-middle part seems to depict more than 10 (spot-like) dots and 8 vertical lines.
- N12-2 is 250 m to the north-west, 10 m from the road. Oriented to north-east-east, it measures 0,4 x 0,75 x 0,4 m. The representation is of a scooping ornithomorphic figure, at the right size of which 2 rows of 7 dots can be observed.

N13 (p. 28)

The rock art site is located 9 km southwest of the southern tip of the village Kodunsky Stanok, in the Kizhinginsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Mongut River, the meaning of which, in the Buryat language, is "silver". The locals call the mountain «Unagan Khan», which, in Buryat, means "fox king". At least 8 rock faces with red ochre images on them were observed:

- N13-1, with a southwestern orientation, and measuring 0,8 x 0,65 x 1,1 x 0,5 m. More than 80 (spot-like) dots are depicted, in addition to the anthropomorphic figures outlined by a square, on the left and on the right, at the top two stylistically similar ornithomorphic figures. A figure in the form of the letter "H" can also be discerned, in the lower part of the composition.
- N13-2 is located 0.7 m to the right of N13-1. Oriented to the southeast, its size is 0.9 x 0.2 x 0.9 x 0.1 m. An anthropomorphic figure is depicted, covered with salt incrustations. Presumably, there are still drawings under the covering, on the left and right.

- N13-3 is 3.5 m to the right of N13-2, at a height of 2.9 m from the base of the rock under it. Oriented south-south-west and 0.65 x 0.95 x 0.5 x 0.85 m large. An ornithomorphic figure is depicted, stylistically similar that found on N13-1. Under it, two dashes may be discerned.
- N13-4 is at only 0.5 m to the right of N13-3. Dimensions: 0.5 x 0.7 x 0.7 x 1.05 m. The site is oriented to the southwest. In the upper part of the rock face there are more than 55 dots (reminiscent of fingerprints) and, above them, three vertical lines.
- N13-5. Located on the southeast side of the same block and oriented to the south east, the measurements are 0.4 x 0.2 x 0.4 x 0.15 m. Two zoomorphic figures are depicted, partially overlapped by whitish formations.
- N13-6 is located 0.7 to the right, and above N13-4. Oriented to the southwest, its size is 0.8 x 0.5 x 1.1 x 0.5 x 0.2 x 1.1 m. An explicitly anthropomorphic figure dominates the site. To its right, one may depict a single and, respectively, three vertical lines.
- N13-7 is on the southeast side of the same block and it is oriented to the southeast. Dimensions: 0.65 x 0.5 x 0.6 x 1.15 m. An anthropomorphic figure, an ornithomorphic figure, and two vertical lines at their left are surrounded by fingerprint-like dots.
- N13-8. Located immediately below N13-7, and also oriented to the southeast. Dimensions: 0.2 x 0.5 x 0.2 x 0.4 m. A zoomorphic figure is depicted.

N14 (no illustration, work in progress)

The rock art site is located 4.8 km southeast of the southern tip of Ust-Orot village, in the Kizhinginsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Khudan (Kodun) River, in the Obogoi-Uber area. We counted at least 11 rock faces with red ochre images:

- N14-1 is located in the lower left part of the outlier, when watched from the southeast. Oriented east-east-south, its size is 1.25 x 0.7 m.
- N14-2. Adjacent, and to the right N-14-1. It has an east-east-south orientation and its size is 1.55 x 0.95 m. In the lower part of the rock face, at a height of 0.5-0.25 m, an unidentifiable figure is depicted.
- N14-3 is 0.2 m to the right of N-14-2, at a height of 0.12 m. It also faces east-east-south and it measures 0.25 x 0.15 m.
- N14-4 is another 0.6 m to the right, at a height of 0.85 m and, like the previous two, it also faces east-east-south. Its size is 0.25 x 0.20 m.
- N14-5 is 0.15 m to the right of and above N14-4, at 1 m above ground. Similarly oriented, and sized 0.9 x 0.35 m.
- N14-6 is 0.4 m to the right of N-14-5 and higher, at 1.4 m. It measures 0.75x0.75 m.
- N14-7 is located immediately below N14-6, AT 0.5 m above ground. Oriented east-east-south, its size is 0.9 x 1.3 m.
- N14-8 is 0.95 m to the right of N-14-7, at a height of 0.25 m and, like the rest, oriented to the southeast. Its size is 0.2 x 0.13 m.
- N14-9 is 0.45 x 0.35 m large and is located immediately above N14-8.
- N14-10 is 0.15 m further to the right, at a height of 1.45 m and, like those mentioned above, it faces east-east-south. Its size is 0.2 x 0.2 m.
- N14-11. Adjacent to the tenth below, at an altitude of 1.25 m. Oriented to the east. Dimensions: 0.2x0.25 m.

N15 (no illustration, due to the spiritual significance of the site)

The rock art site is located on Mount Chelsana, near the village of Kizhinga, in the Kizhinginsky District of the Republic of Buryatia. The mountain is revered by the local population and collective worship rites, known as «oboo», are regularly held here. According to legend, the palace of the spirit of Buural Baabay is at this location. Ornithomorphic figures and dots decorate the rock but, for the documentation of this holy place, the permission of a Buddhist religious authority is required.

N16 (p. 29)

The rock art site is located 8.6 km - in a straight line - north-northeast of the northern outskirts of the village Alan, in the Khorinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, in the area of Khotogor (wich, in the Buryat language means "curved"). At least 8 rock faces with red ochre images can be distinguished:

- N16-1 is located on the left side of the cliff, when observed from the south, at a height of 1.25 - 1.3 m. It is oriented to the west-west-south and its size is 0.4 x 0.27 x 0.15 m. A single anthropomorphic figure, tilted to the left, is visible.
- N16-2 is 3 m to the right of N16-1, at a height of 2.15 m. Oriented to the west, its dimensions are 0.25 x 0.15 x 0.1 x 0.12 x 0.6 x 0.3 m. Two anthropomorphic figures are depicted and, below them, another figure with unidentifiable outlines. The surface is badly damaged.
- N16-3 is located 0.4 m to the right, at a height of 1.6 m. It is oriented to the south and its size is 0.3 x 0.25 x 0.35 x 0.4 x 0.1 m. Dots are depicted.
- N16-4 is 0.3 m to the right of N16-3, at a height of 2.1 m. It faces south-south-west and is 0.15 x 0.05 x 0.08 x 0.12 m large. It depicts a presumably ornithomorphic figure.
- N16-5. To the right of N16-3 and at a lower - 1.2 m - height. Dimensions: 0.25 x 0.15 x 0.3 x 0.2 m. It depicts dots ordered in rows.
- N16-6 is also to the right of N16-3, 0.9 m from it, and at a height of 1.45 m. Oriented west-west-north, it measures 0.23 x 0.22 x 0.2 x 0.15 x 0.1 x 0.2 x 0.12 m. The depiction resembles a figure riding a horse.
- N16-7. On the south side of the same block, at a height of 1.45 m, and facing straight south. Dimensions: 0.15 x 0.09 x 0.05 x 0.2 x 0.08 m. The depiction is of an apparently anthropomorphic, but also possibly ornithomorphic figure.
- N16-8. Adjacent, and to the left of N16-7, at a height of 1.6 m. It faces west-west-south and its size is 0.2 x 0.05 x 0.22 x 0.05 m. Two lines are depicted.

N17 (pp. 30-31)

The site is located 5.4 km - in a straight line - north of the northern outskirts of the village of Egita, in the Eravinsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the right bank of the Zun-Narin-Gorkhon (also known as Anyulka) River. At least 8 surfaces adorned with red ochre images - in the same hue - were observed:

- N17-1, in the center of the cliff, when seen from the south-west, at a height of 1 m. Dimensions: 0.95 x 0.5 x 0.5 x 0.8 x 0.8 m. Oriented to the south-south-west, the composition depicts over 100 dots with 3 presumably anthropomorphic figures under them.
- N17-2 is located 1.4 m to the right of N17-1, on a neighboring block. Dimensions: 2.3 x 2.3 x 2.7 x 0.7 m. The composition, which depicts over 100 dots organized in rows, faces the southeast. In the upper-left part of the composition, placed between the dots, an anthropomorphic figure is depicted. In the middle part of the composition, also between the dots, 4 presumably anthropomorphic figures are drawn. Below, under the dots, a likely zoomorphic figure complements the composition.
- N17-3 is to the right of N17-2, on a neighboring block, and oriented to the west. Dimensions: 0.7 x 1.1 x 0.5 x 1.1 x 0.7 x 2.2 m. The figures are presented in two groups. The dots are depicted in the middle part of the surface. At least four rows of 2, 4, and 6 dots are depicted in the lower part of the surface, and an anthropomorphic figure is below them.
- N17-4 shares the same rock with N17-3 and is on the block's southern and southeastern sides, to the right of N17-3. Dimensions: 1.2 x 0.9 x 1.2 x 1 x 1 x 1.1 m. In the center of the composition there are 3 anthropomorphic figures and, above them, at least 5 rows of 4, respectively, 6 dots. Below and to the left of the anthropomorphs there are additional dots and more images which, unfortunately, are barely discernable.
- N17-5 is further to the right, at the foot of the cliff. Dimensions: 3.3 x 1 x 3.3 x 0.85 m. Oriented to south-southeast, the composition depicts at least 15 anthropomorphic figures distributed in rows organized in three groups. Lines and dots - randomly distributed, respectively organized in rows - complement the composition. In the upper-right part of the composition there seems to be an additional, but damaged figurative image.
- N17-6, to the right, is located at a height of 0.9-1 m. Dimensions: 1.6 x 1.3 x 0.8 x 1.9 x 1.5 m. It is oriented to the south-southeast and it depicts at least one anthropomorphic figure surrounded by dots and lines, with a cruciform image placed between them.
- N17-7 is on the same block with N17-6 but separated by a crack in the rock. It is located at a height of 1.1 m and its size is 1.4 x 1.1 x 1.2 x 0.8 m. Like N17-6, it also faces south-southeast. The composition seems to depict 2 anthropomorphic surrounded by vertical lines. A cluster of at least 30 dots can be seen in the upper right part of the rock face.
- N17-8 is on the same block with N17-6 and N17-7, but above these, at a height of about 2 m. It also faces south-southeast. Dimensions: 1.6 x 1.2 x 0.6 x 1.5 m. At the bottom of the surface rows of dots are depicted.

N18 (p. 32)

The site is located 4.5 km - in a straight line - north of the northern outskirts of the village of Egita, in the Eravninsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the left bank of the Zun-Narin-Gorkhon, and 1.3 km south-east of N17. At least one rock face with drawings can be distinguished (N18-1). The drawings are located on the south side of the block, at the top of a rocky ridge. Oriented straight to the south, the size of the composition is 0.8 x 1.1 x 1.3 x 1.2 m. The composition depicts at least ten rows of red ochre colored dots, which are located in the upper-right part of the rock face.

N19 (Shulutsky Datsan, p. 32)

This rock art site was previously documented in the literature and mentioned as the Shulutsky Datsan (*Pamyatniki arkheologii*, 2011, pp. 204-205). A composition consisting of 45 dots arranged in 4 horizontal rows is documented in the abovementioned anthology. However, taking more photographs and enhancing them by applying D-Stretch enabled us to identify additional images. Together with the known composition, at least 4 rock faces adorned with red ochre images could be identified:

- N19-1 (previously known) is located in the middle of the cliff, at a height of 1.1 m. It is oriented to the south and its size is 0.45 x 0.07 x 0.5 x 0.15 m. The left and middle parts of the surface are partially covered with white smudges. At least 45 dots arranged in 4 horizontal rows seem to be depicted.
- N19-2 is 2.5 m to the left of N19-1 and it is oriented to the southwest. According to the photograph, its size is about 1.3 x 2 m and it is at a height of about 1.3 m. In the upper part there are 2 anthropomorphic depictions, in the middle part 3 rows of dots and, at the bottom, 2 presumably anthropomorphic figures.
- N19-3 is at a distance of 5.5 m from N19-1, at a height of 1.1 m. The composition is oriented to the southeast and its size is 1.2 x 0.2 x 1.3 x 0.3 m. The rock face is partially covered with white smudges that overlay some images. The depictions are located in the upper part. To their left there are 2 rows of dots, while to their right, apparently 3 rows of dots.
- N19-4 is located at about 1.5 m to the left of N19-1. The composition depicts 3 rows of at least 24 dots. Below these, 2 rows of 4 dots each, and 2 cruciform figures can be discerned.

N20 (Isinga, p. 33)

This previously documented (Tivanenko, 1990, p. 21) and well-known famous rock art site is located on the western outskirts of the village of Isinga, in the Eravninsky District of the Republic of Buryatia, on the lakeshore. According to the description (*ibid.*), two groups of drawings consisting of dots and cruciform signs were identified. Unfortunately, the documentation does not specify the exact location of the rocks on which the depictions were found but, during this survey, they were identified:

- N20-1 is located on the right edge of the cliff, when seen from the northwest. It has a north-north-west orientation and its dimensions are 0.35 x 1.35 x 0.55 x 1.3 m. Two cross-shaped figures of 50 cm each are depicted in this composition and, under a thick layer of soot, it seems that a number of dots are also present.
- N20-2 is 2 m to the left of N20-1 and it is facing the west. The size of the composition is 0.4 x 1.3 x 0.7 x 1 x 2.2 m. Dots and lines seem to be depicted.

References

- Antonova, Y. E. and V. I. Tashak (2013)
Barun-Lamkhe - drevneye svyatilishche v Zapadnom Zabaykal'ye [Barun-Lamkhe - an ancient sanctuary Western Transbaikalia] Integratsiya arkheologicheskikh i etnograficheskikh issledovaniy [Integration of archaeological and ethnographic research]. Irkutsk, pp. 233-236. (in Russian)
- Davydov, D. (1856)
O drevnikh pamyatnikakh i mogil'nykh ostatkakh aborigenov Zabaykal'skoy oblasti Verkhneudinskogo okruga [On the remains of ancient monuments and graves of the natives of the Transbaikal region of the Verkhneudinsky district]. *Zapiski Sibirskogo otdela RGO* [Notes of the Siberian Department of the Russian Geographical Society], pp. 89-100. (in Russ.)
- Kastren, M. A. (1860)
Puteshestviye po Laplandii, Severnoy Rossii i Sibiri v 1838—1844, 1845—1849 gg. [Traveling in Lapland, Northern Russia and Siberia in 1838–1844, 1845–1849.], St. Petersburg. p. 503. (in Russ.)
- Khamzina, E. A. (1982)
Arkheologicheskie pamyatniki Buryatii [Archaeological sites of Buryatia]. Novosibirsk, 152 p. (in Russ.)
- Lbova, L. V. and E. A. Khamzina (1999)
Karta arkheologicheskikh pamyatnikov Buryatii [Map of the archaeological sites of Buryatia]. Ulan-Ude, 241 p. (in Russ.)
- Okladnikov, A. P. and V. D. Zaporozhskaya (1969)
Petroglify Zabaikal'ya [Petroglyphs of Transbaikalia]. Vol. 1, Leningrad, 220 p. (in Russ.)
- Okladnikov, A. P. and V. D. Zaporozhskaya (1970)
Petroglify Zabaikal'ya [Petroglyphs of Transbaikalia]. Vol. 2, Leningrad, 264 p. (in Russ.)
- Popov, V. V. (1928)
Otchet o deyatel'nosti Buryat-Mongol'skogo Obshchestva imeni D. Banzarova s 1 oktyabrya 1926 po 1 yanvarya 1928 gg. [Report on the activities of the D. Banzarov Buryat-Mongolian Society from October 1, 1926 to January 1, 1928.] *Buryatiyovedenie* [Buryat Science], № 4, pp. 155-168. Ulan-Ude. (in Russ.)
- Tashak, V. I. (2011)
Drevnee svyatilishche v doline Alana (Zapadnoye Zabaikal'e) [The ancient sanctuary in the valley of the Alan River (Western Transbaikalia)]. *Drevnie kul'tiry Mongolii i Baikal'skoy Sibiri* [Ancient cultures of Mongolia and Baikal Siberia], Issue 2, pp. 251–256. Irkutsk. (in Russ.)
- Tashak, V. I. (2013)
Territorial'naya organizatsiya drevnego svyatilishcha Barun-Alan-1 v Zapadnom Zabaikal'e [Spatial organization of the ancient sanctuary Barun-Alan-1 in Western Transbaikalia]. *Vestnik Tomskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. Istorika* [The Bulletin of Tomsk State University. History]. № 3, pp. 172–176. (in Russ.)
- Tivanenko, A. V. (1990)
Drevneye naskal'noye iskusstvo Buryatii [Ancient rock art of Buryatia]. Novosibirsk, 208 p. (in Russ.)
- Tsybiktarov, V. A. (2011)
Petroglify Zabaykal'ya (formirovaniye istochnikovoy bazy, istoriografiya i voprosy istoriko-kul'turnoy interpretatsii) [Petroglyphs of Transbaikalia (the formation of the source base, historiography and questions of historical and cultural interpretation)]. Ulan-Ude, 276 p. (in Russ.)
- (2011)
Pamyatniki arkheologii [Archaeological Sites]. Ulan-Ude, 397 p. (in Russ.)

Tracings

N1, N2

N3

N4

N5

N 6, N7, N8, N9, N10

N11, N12

N13

N16

N17

N17 (cont.)

N18, N19

N20

Photographs

N2-2 and N2-3

N2-2 and N2-3 (D-Stretch)

N2-2.

N2-2 (D-Stretch)

N13-5

N5-5

N5-5 (D-Stretch)

